

DORES: a streamlined software for the design and operational planning of photovoltaic and storage systems in buildings and communities

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Photovoltaics
Simulation software
Energy storage
Energy communities
Energy management strategies

ABSTRACT

Photovoltaics (PV) and electrical energy storage (EES) are key technologies for decarbonizing buildings and communities. Yet, planning integrated PV storage systems remains challenging due to solar variability, battery degradation, and economic uncertainty, and it requires simulating operational strategies to support informed design. Existing tools often address only part of this challenge, focusing on PV yield, economics, or microgrid optimization, without combining technical, economic, and environmental indicators across both building and community scales.

To address this gap, this paper introduces DORES (Design and Operational Planning of Renewable Energy Systems), a modular and user-friendly simulation tool for PV-storage integration. DORES models load profiles (measured or generated), PV systems, and batteries, and implements multiple energy management strategies, ranging from rule-based control to optimization-based methods that include battery wear costs. The tool automatically calculates key performance indicators (self-sufficiency, self-consumption, net present value, life cycle cost, and CO₂ savings) through a graphical interface developed in MATLAB. Validation against monitored data and a benchmark commercial tool (PV*SOL) shows high accuracy, with deviations in key indicators typically below 5%. In addition, DORES enables scenario testing at the community scale, supporting aggregated prosumer systems and shared storage assessment.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and motivation

Buildings account for nearly 40 % of global energy use and a substantial share of carbon emissions, making them a priority for decarbonization efforts [1]. As cities evolve, on-site generation, particularly photovoltaics (PV), and Electrical Energy Storage (EES) systems, are becoming central to improving energy autonomy, lowering operational costs, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) [2]. Recent declines in solar technology costs, coupled with policy initiatives, have accelerated PV adoption in residential and commercial buildings [3].

However, integrating PV with EES is key to maximizing self-consumption, enhancing system resilience, and minimizing peak demand charges [4]. Despite these benefits, designing and operating integrated PV/Storage solutions remains a complex task. Technical challenges include managing intermittent solar generation, modeling battery degradation, and ensuring reliability during extended outages

[5]. Economic challenges arise from high upfront storage costs, uncertain market incentives, and the need for robust valuation of resilience benefits [3]. Meanwhile, policy and regulatory frameworks have not always kept pace with new technologies, leaving unclear mechanisms for grid services such as peak shaving and demand response [3].

Additionally, existing simulation and optimization tools often fail to capture technical, economic, and resilience objectives simultaneously [5]. They tend to emphasize cost optimization for grid-connected operation while overlooking islanded operation modes or advanced control strategies [4,5]. As a result, decision-makers lack comprehensive tools to confidently design and compare different PV-plus-EES configurations at both building and district scales. Addressing these gaps is critical for advancing energy independence and sustainable urban development.

1.2. State of the art

The integration of PV systems with energy storage has been widely

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2026.101531>

Received 27 April 2025; Received in revised form 11 November 2025; Accepted 6 January 2026

Available online 7 January 2026

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explored through various modeling tools and simulation platforms. Early efforts primarily relied on general-purpose building energy simulation tools such as EnergyPlus [6] and TRNSYS [7] or techno-economic microgrid planning software such as HOMER [8]. While these platforms are valuable for assessing energy consumption, renewable energy yields, and basic grid interactions, their capacity to model advanced battery dynamics, implement flexible control strategies, or perform scalable analyses across multiple buildings within an Energy Community (EC) remains limited [9,10].

Building-oriented tools such as EnergyPlus offer detailed insights into load profiles and thermal performance, but were not designed to optimize battery operations or include comprehensive economic indicators such as net present value (NPV) or life cycle cost (LCC) [11]. Conversely, microgrid design tools like HOMER emphasize off-grid or hybrid systems, focusing on simplified techno-economic evaluations that often overlook complex operational dynamics such as real-time grid interactions, coordinated multi-building operations, or resilience assessments [12].

In recent years, more advanced frameworks have emerged that incorporate detailed component-level modeling, optimization algorithms, and multi-objective analyses. These tools can address strategies such as peak shaving, time-of-use load shifting, and day-ahead price arbitrage [13,14]. However, many of these solutions remain focused on single-building contexts or require intensive customization to assess multi-building or community-scale energy systems effectively [9]. Few provide a streamlined interface that connects high-level feasibility

studies and detailed operational modeling [15]. Recent studies also stress the role of digitized energy systems and open-access platforms as enablers of carbon-neutral urban transitions, as demonstrated by the BIPV-city platform [16]. This lack of integration complicates decision-making for planners and stakeholders eager to explore alternative system designs or control strategies without extensive technical expertise.

Consequently, there is a clear demand for a software solution that bridges these gaps: providing robust technical analysis while remaining user-friendly, supporting both building-scale and community-scale applications, and offering actionable insights across technical, economic, and environmental dimensions. As summarized in Table 1, existing tools contribute valuable methods, but they are generally limited to either PV yield estimation, techno-economic sizing, or case-specific optimization. Few integrate advanced control strategies, community-scale modeling, and combined technical, economic, and environmental evaluation within a single, user-oriented interface.

Beyond general-purpose simulation environments, several recent studies have proposed advanced control or sizing strategies for PV-battery systems in grid-connected settings. For instance, [17] presents a rule-based control approach that uses day-ahead forecasts to limit both demand and feed-in peaks while preserving state-of-charge balance. Similarly, [18] emphasizes techno-economic sizing of PV and battery systems under local tariff conditions, employing simplified operational strategies. Other works, such as [19], investigate the impact of forecast errors on battery scheduling and propose corrective mechanisms, while [20] extends to multi-energy systems using model predictive control.

Table 1
Comparison of representative tools and academic studies for PV–battery integration.

Tool/study	Type	Simulation & control	Sizing/optimization	Economic analysis	CO ₂ /Env.	Validation/notes	Limitations
HOMER Pro [21]	Commercial	Hourly sim; LF/CC modes	Yes (search-based)	NPV, IRR, sensitivity	Basic (fuel/grid mix)	Industry standard	Simplified dispatch, weak real-time/grid interaction
PV*SOL [22]	Commercial	PV focus: shading analysis	Limited	Detailed finance (NPV, payback)	Basic (emissions factor)	Widely validated	Strong financial modeling, weak EMS/community
SAM [23]	Public/Academic	Hourly–sub-hourly; predefined dispatch	Limited	Detailed finance (NPV, payback)	Basic (emissions factor)	Widely validated	Strong financial modeling, weak EMS/community
iHOGA [24]	Commercial/Academic	Hourly; simple rule dispatch	Yes (GA-based)	NPC, NPV	Basic	Validated vs. HOMER	Focused on off-grid, limited community scope
SAMA [25]	Open-source	Hourly; metaheuristic dispatch	Yes (multi-objective GA/PSO)	LCOE, payback	Optional	Benchmarked	Case-specific, complex setup
DER-CAM [26]	Academic	MILP-based dispatch	Yes (co-optimization MILP)	Min-cost	Yes	Validated in real microgrids	Complex, expert-only use
oemof.solph [27]	Open-source library	Flexible MILP dispatch	Yes	User-defined	Yes	Academic studies	Requires coding, not user-friendly
Ficus [28]	Open-source library	Optimized dispatch (LP)	Yes (capacity expansion)	Min-cost	Yes	Academic use	Library only, steep learning curve
ESN [29]	Open-source framework	High-res sim, user-defined control	No	Operational costs	Yes (component-based)	Case studies	No sizing, no GUI
TRNSYS [7]	Academic tool	Component-based, hourly	No	Basic	Optional	Long history validation	Complex setup, limited EMS
Manojkumar et al. [17]	Academic study	Rule-based, forecast-driven peak shaving	No	Cost savings	Indirect	Case study	Not generalizable, no platform
Saleem et al. [30]	Academic study	Stochastic MPC for residential complexes (PV + BESS + EV)	Yes	Cost + reliability	Indirect	Validated in a residential complex simulation	Complex, not user-friendly
Ragab et al. [31]	Academic study	Community PV + shared BESS sizing	Yes (MILP)	Economic feasibility	Optional	Tested in community-scale scenarios	Case-specific, limited EMS features
Rus-Casas et al. [32]	Academic study	Joint EMS + sizing for PV–BESS	Yes	NPV, payback	Basic	Validated on a residential case study	Single building, no community aggregation
Hesse [33]	Academic study	PV–BESS modeling, rule-based EMS	Yes (sizing + aging)	Economic feasibility	No	Simulated and compared with HOMER	Focuses on sizing, not community

*LF = load-following; CC = cycle-charging; MILP = mixed-integer linear programming; LCOE = levelized cost of electricity; NPC = net present cost.

These contributions demonstrate the growing interest in combining PV and storage with intelligent control. However, they remain case-specific and do not provide a generalized simulation framework. This highlights a clear research gap: the lack of a unified, user-friendly platform that integrates advanced control strategies (including optimization with battery wear costs), supports community-scale aggregation, and combines automatic load profile generation, storage sizing, and KPI-based evaluation in a single environment.

1.3. Aim and contributions

In response to the identified gaps, this work presents DORES (Design and Operational Planning of Renewable Energy Systems), a modular GUI-based tool that integrates rule-based and optimization-based control strategies (including battery wear costs), supports both building- and community-scale modeling, and provides simultaneous technical, economic, and environmental evaluation. This dual scope reflects the increasing policy and research emphasis on collective self-consumption and local energy sharing, emphasizing the need for tools that address both individual buildings and aggregated energy communities.

1.3.1. Overview of the software

DORES is developed to simulate energy systems for individual buildings and large-scale communities, accommodating a variety of building archetypes. It supports multiple energy sources, including Building-Applied Photovoltaics (BAPV), Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV), and EES systems. It takes into account electricity load profiles at both building and community levels. For scenarios lacking hourly load data, the tool provides normalized load profiles tailored to various consumption types (e.g., residential, industrial, kindergarten, and public lighting).

A central feature of the software is the optimization of EES capacity, which can be tailored to meet objectives such as peak-shaving or standalone, off-grid operations. The software integrates various control strategies, enabling users to simulate, evaluate, and compare energy flows and operational behaviors for both buildings and entire ECs. Beyond technical modeling, DORES performs automated performance evaluations, calculating key metrics such as self-consumption, self-sufficiency, electricity costs, and battery utilization. Economic and environmental indicators, including NPV, LCCs based on capital (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX), and CO₂ emissions reductions, are also included to support a comprehensive system assessment.

With its modular and scalable architecture, DORES enables users to make informed design decisions regarding renewable generation capacity, storage sizing, and strategies for achieving grid independence.

1.3.2. Purpose and scope of the software

The primary objective of DORES is to provide a comprehensive and user-friendly platform for assessing and optimizing renewable energy systems in the built environment. The tool supports detailed energy planning by allowing users to simulate and forecast the performance of PV and EES technologies across multiple building types and consumption profiles. It also supports grid interaction studies, examining how renewable systems engage with the utility grid while highlighting opportunities to enhance flexibility.

Beyond software implementation, DORES introduces several technical novelties. These include integrated multi-scale modeling at both the building and community levels, hybrid energy management strategies (rule-based and optimization-based with explicit battery amortization costs), the incorporation of battery wear into the optimization framework, and the automatic generation of realistic load profiles when measured data are unavailable. In addition, DORES provides a comprehensive KPI framework covering technical (Sc, Ss, FI), economic (NPV, LCC), and environmental (CO₂ savings) indicators, offering a level of integration not available in existing tools.

Additionally, DORES enables users to optimize energy management

by testing various operational strategies aimed at reducing costs, minimizing GHG emissions, improving efficiency, and enhancing energy autonomy. Thanks to its adaptable design, DORES is well-suited to academic and professional settings. It can serve as a valuable resource for teaching and research activities, as well as for the practical planning and operation of building-scale and district-scale energy systems.

1.4. Paper organization

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) provides a detailed description of the core simulation modules, including load profile estimation, PV system modeling, battery storage analysis, and control strategy implementation. [Section 3](#) describes the software architecture and user interface. [Section 4](#) presents the validation of the tool through comparisons with measured data and the commercial software PV*SOL, highlighting its accuracy and reliability. [Section 5](#) discusses the interpretation of results, practical implications for energy optimization in buildings and communities, and the main limitations of the current version. Finally, [section 6](#) concludes the paper by summarizing the key features and practical relevance of the DORES software in promoting sustainable energy management in the built environment.

2. Methodology and models

This section outlines the main theoretical models, computational methods, and system components underlying the DORES tool. The methodology enables comprehensive simulation and optimization of PV and EES systems, addressing the complex interactions between generation, storage, load demand, and grid dynamics at both building and community scales.

DORES incorporates several key modules, including load profile generation, PV system modeling, battery storage simulation, and the implementation of energy management control strategies. Each module is integrated within a unified framework to deliver actionable insights across technical, economic, and environmental dimensions. [Fig. 1](#) illustrates the general system diagram of the DORES, including the energy flows and the control layer. The software also calculates key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess system performance, facilitating robust

Fig. 1. General system diagram of the DORES tool.

comparisons of design alternatives.

The following subsections describe the underlying models and algorithms, establishing the foundation for the software implementation described later in Section 3.

2.1. Load profile estimation

The Load Profile Estimation feature of the tool is a core functionality designed to generate hourly electricity load profiles tailored to user-defined inputs, such as building typology and energy consumption patterns. The tool supports a wide range of building types, including residential, commercial, and public facilities. It accurately reflects typical usage scenarios by considering factors such as occupancy, appliance usage, and seasonal variations. These realistic load profiles form the foundation for energy management simulations and the optimization of renewable energy systems.

DORES enables users to directly import monitored energy consumption data for buildings equipped with smart or digital energy meters, enabling precise and customized energy system analyses. However, in cases where such data is unavailable, the software provides pre-built normalized load profiles sourced from the Czech electricity and gas market operator (OTE) [34]. These profiles are categorized by relevant building typologies and energy supply systems (see Table 2) and offer an adaptable simulation baseline.

The normalized profiles are adjusted based on the electricity consumption inputs provided by the user for the selected analysis period. The goal is to find the optimized value of energy consumption E^* that minimizes the nonlinear curve fitting optimization problem subject to the constraint $E > 0$ described as:

$$E^* = \min_E \sum_{i=1}^N (E \cdot TDDX_i - Em_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

where $TDDX_i$ represents the selected normalized profile demand value at hour i , and Em_i is the measured energy consumption data.

While standardized load profiles provide a useful baseline for analysis, they are aggregated representations derived from distribution system operator datasets and may not capture the full variability of individual buildings (e.g., short-term peaks or unusual load events). For this reason, measured profiles remain the preferred option whenever available. The standardized profiles should therefore be regarded as an approximation, suitable primarily for feasibility studies or early-stage design, while more detailed measured datasets are recommended for

Table 2

Categorized electricity profiles according to Czechia's most relevant building typologies.

ID	Consumer category	Type of consumption
TDD1	Commercial	Electricity consumption from small shops or offices, mainly lighting and equipment used during daytime hours.
TDD2	Commercial	Electricity consumption of retail or service businesses operating into the evening includes lighting, HVAC, and appliances.
TDD3	Commercial	Typical for restaurants, small production, or 24/7 operations, including cooling and ventilation, with a more stable daily load.
TDD4	Residential	Household consumption without electric space heating, covering appliances, lighting, and electronics.
TDD5	Residential	Households with boilers or water heaters include base consumption plus electricity used for water heating.
TDD6	Residential	Households that use direct or accumulated electric heating often have higher evening and nighttime loads.
TDD7	Residential	Households equipped with heat pumps for heating and possibly cooling.
TDD8	Commercial	Electricity consumption for street and outdoor public lighting, operated by photocells or timers.

operational control-oriented analyses.

2.2. PV system modeling

The electrical output of the PV systems is calculated using a simplified model based on the effective PV area, installed nominal power capacity, module and inverter efficiencies, and temperature correction using plane-of-array solar irradiance (G_{POA}) and module temperature (T_m). The core relationship used is given by Eq. (2):

$$P_{PV} = A_m N_m \eta_m \eta_{inv} G_{POA} \bullet (1 - \gamma(T_m - T_{STC})) \quad (2)$$

where P_{PV} is the PV power output [W] and A_m is the module area [m²]. N_m is the number of modules. γ is the module temperature coefficient [%/°C], and T_{STC} is the reference module temperature (25 °C). The inverter efficiency is represented by η_{inv} , and η_m is the PV module efficiency obtained based on the PV panel's nominal power divided by the solar irradiance at STC divided by the module area.

The Perez anisotropic irradiance model was used to convert global horizontal (G_h) irradiance into plane-of-array irradiance (G_{POA}), incorporating site-specific geographic parameters (latitude, longitude), array orientation (tilt, azimuth), and solar geometry (zenith and azimuth angles) [35,36].

Furthermore, to consider the temperature effects on the PV output performance, the PV module temperature is calculated differently for roof-mounted and façade installations. For roof-mounted installations, the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT) method was applied [37] as shown in Eq. (3):

$$T_m = T_a + \frac{NOCT - 20}{800} \bullet G_{POA} \quad (3)$$

where T_m is the module temperature [°C], T_a is the ambient temperature [°C], and NOCT is the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature provided by the module manufacturer.

Regarding the façade-integrated PV installations placed within closed cavities, the module temperature was estimated using a linear empirical approach, as described by Eq. (4) [38]:

$$T_m = T_a + \frac{\alpha G_{POA} (1 - \eta_m)}{U} \quad (4)$$

Where the constant α represents the absorption coefficient (typically = 0.9). U is the heat loss factor; its value depends on the mounting configuration. Experiments based on measurements from various installations suggested $U = 15 \text{ W/(m}^2\text{K)}$ for poorly ventilated and insulated PV backside [38].

2.3. Battery/EES modeling and sizing

The battery mathematical model, previously described and validated in our earlier works [39,40], is used to simulate its behavior. The battery normalized state-of-charge (SOC_n) is expressed as a percentage over time t , and estimated using Eq. (5):

$$SOC_n(t) = SOC_i + \frac{1}{SOC_m} \int \left(\frac{\eta P_{bat}}{3600} - \frac{D SOC_n(t - \tau) SOC_m}{3600} \right) dt \quad (5)$$

where SOC_i is the initial state of charge [%], SOC_m is the battery's maximum capacity [Wh], P_{bat} represents the battery power (negative for charging, positive for discharging), η is charge/discharge efficiency, D accounts for self-discharge, and τ is the internal simulation time step.

The model is configurable to match real storage system characteristics, considering maximum charge/discharge powers, depth-of-discharge (DoD), and system losses, all crucial for accurate dynamic performance assessment.

Validation results from previous studies confirm that the model closely aligns with measured data, with RMSE values below 5 %, demonstrating its reliability in reproducing real battery behavior

[39,40].

In addition to battery modeling and simulation, the software incorporates the sizing methodology for EES, published in [41]. The sizing approach is based on the energy balance between generation and demand and allows for precise storage dimensioning in buildings or communities with multiple energy sources. The EES can be sized for a defined period ranging from days to several years, depending on specific needs and objectives (e.g., providing services during a particular season). The EES capacity can also be determined to fulfil ambitious targets such as conceiving fully autonomous (standalone) buildings/communities, supporting grid stability/congestion through peak shaving, and optimizing EES sizing based on economic targets.

Beyond dynamic SOC evolution, DORES also accounts for battery degradation by calculating cumulative full equivalent cycles from the SOC trajectory over the selected simulation period [42]. Comparing these calculated cycles with the reference values provided in the battery's technical data sheet enables an estimation of wear-related costs. These costs are then integrated into the optimization framework through the battery amortization term (see Section 2.4). Although simplified, this approach provides a realistic trade-off between short-term cost savings and long-term battery longevity.

2.4. Energy management control strategies

The developed tool integrates various control strategies to simulate the operation of buildings and communities equipped with PV and electrical storage systems. These energy management strategies are categorized into rule-based and optimization-based approaches.

Two widely used rule-based strategies are implemented in the software:

- Load-Following Control Strategy (LFCS): a well-established energy management approach designed to maximize local PV utilization. It achieves this by storing excess PV energy during the day and discharging it at night, reducing grid dependency. LFCS is widely used in commercial PV-battery simulation software [7,21,38]. Further details on its operation can be found in our previous works [43,44].
- Peak-Shaving Control Strategy (PSCS): another well-established control algorithm ensuring that grid energy consumption remains within a pre-defined maximum limit, preventing excess demand that could incur additional costs or penalties. This strategy optimally balances cost efficiency and grid stability, mitigating peak loads and reducing grid stress [45].

Regarding the optimization-based energy management strategies, the software incorporates two smart energy management strategies (SEMS) formulated as a linear programming (LP) problem [42,46]. The objective is to minimize the total electricity cost over a 24-hour horizon, considering PV forecasts, load consumption forecasts, battery storage specifications, and the electricity grid. In addition, the market interaction is represented by a user-defined dynamic day-ahead electricity price profile. Both purchase and sell-back rates are considered by the linear programming framework, ensuring that control strategies reflect realistic market dynamics (purchasing when electricity is cheap and selling when it is expensive).

$$\min \sum_{t=1}^{24} C_{grid}(t) \bullet P_{grid}^{buy}(t) - C_{sell}(t) \bullet P_{grid}^{sell}(t) \quad (6)$$

where, $C_{grid}(t)$ is the electricity price for purchasing from the grid, and $C_{sell}(t)$ is the selling price of electricity back to the grid.

To ensure realistic and technically feasible operation, the optimization problem is bounded by a set of physical and operational constraints. The power balance constraint guarantees that energy demand is met at each timestep, preventing infeasible solutions where the load is undersupplied. Battery constraints are imposed to reflect manufacturer

specifications and electrochemical limits, including charge/discharge efficiency, maximum power ratings, and state-of-charge boundaries. These conditions are widely adopted in energy management system formulations to avoid battery overcharging, deep discharging, or unrealistic performance assumptions [42,46]. Finally, grid import and export limits are included to represent technical restrictions of grid connections and regulatory requirements related to ancillary services or congestion management.

Together, the following constraints ensure that the optimization framework remains consistent with real-world system behavior and safety considerations.

- **Power Balance Constraint:** The total power demand at each time step must be met:

$$P_{load}(t) = P_{PV}(t) + P_{bat}^{dis}(t) + P_{grid}^{buy}(t) - P_{bat}^{ch}(t) - P_{grid}^{sell}(t) \quad (7)$$

where: $P_{load}(t)$ is the forecasted building/community load consumption at time t . $P_{grid}^{buy}(t)$ and $P_{grid}^{sell}(t)$ are the power purchased from the grid and the power sold back to the grid at time t . $P_{bat}^{ch}(t)$ and $P_{bat}^{dis}(t)$ are the charge/discharge powers of the battery at time t .

- **Battery Constraints:** the battery charging and discharging must respect the charge/discharge efficiencies ($\eta_{ch} = \eta_{dis}$), maximum charge/discharge powers ($P_{bat,max}^{ch}$, $P_{bat,max}^{dis}$), and limits linked to the SOC_{min} and SOC_{max} as follows:

$$SOC(t) = SOC(t-1) + \eta_{ch} P_{bat}^{ch}(t) - \frac{P_{bat}^{dis}(t)}{\eta_{dis}} \quad (8)$$

$$SOC_{min} \leq SOC(t) \leq SOC_{max} \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq P_{bat}^{ch}(t) \leq P_{bat,max}^{ch}, \quad 0 \leq P_{bat}^{dis}(t) \leq P_{bat,max}^{dis} \quad (10)$$

- **Grid Constraints:** To include grid ancillary services and reduce grid congestion, both import and export powers must be within allowed limits ($P_{grid,max}^{buy}$, $P_{grid,max}^{sell}$):

$$0 \leq P_{grid}^{buy}(t) \leq P_{grid,max}^{buy}, \quad 0 \leq P_{grid}^{sell}(t) \leq P_{grid,max}^{sell} \quad (11)$$

The optimization problem is implemented in MATLAB using the key functions and toolboxes such as "otimproblem" and "optimvar" to define the optimization problem and "linprog" to solve the LP problem.

The second SEMS incorporates an additional cost term to account for battery wear caused by charge/discharge cycles. This is represented by the Battery Amortization Price $C_{bat}(t)$ (€/kWh), which quantifies the cost associated with battery degradation over time. Consequently, the total battery usage cost is now determined by both the electricity price and the amortization cost, ensuring a more balanced trade-off between cost savings and battery longevity. To reflect this, the objective function is modified as follows:

$$\min \sum_{t=1}^{24} \left(C_{grid}(t) \bullet P_{grid}^{buy}(t) - C_{sell}(t) \bullet P_{grid}^{sell}(t) + C_{bat}(t) \bullet (P_{bat}^{ch}(t) + P_{bat}^{dis}(t)) \right) \quad (12)$$

To ensure that battery usage only occurs when it is economically justified, the following threshold condition was added:

$$C_{grid,max} - C_{grid,min} \geq C_{bat}(t) \quad (13)$$

where $C_{grid,min}$ and $C_{grid,max}$ are the lowest and highest electricity prices over the 24 h, respectively. This approach ensures that small fluctuations in electricity price do not trigger unnecessary charge/discharge cycles, thereby extending battery lifespan.

Fig. 2 shows the simplified flowcharts representing the logic behind

Fig. 2. Simplified flowcharts of the different energy management strategies.

the functioning of the different control strategies implemented in the DORES tool.

2.5. Key performance indicators (KPIs)

The toolbox provides a detailed analysis of building/energy community performance by calculating various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These metrics offer valuable insights into the technical feasibility and economic, environmental, and operational effectiveness of the whole energy system. Some selected KPI metrics are described in the subsections below.

2.5.1. Technical metrics

The Self-Consumption (S_c) quantifies the fraction of the locally generated PV energy that is either directly consumed or stored within an energy storage system rather than being exported to the grid. The Self-Sufficiency (S_s) measures the extent to which the building or community can meet its energy demand using its own PV generation, indicating its level of energy autonomy. These indicators are mathematically defined as follows [40]:

$$S_c(\%) = 100 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{E_{exp}}{E_{pv}}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$S_s(\%) = 100 \left(1 - \frac{E_{imp}}{E_L}\right) \quad (15)$$

where E_{exp} is the PV excess energy exported to the grid, E_{pv} is the accumulated PV energy, E_{imp} is the energy taken from the utility grid, and E_L represents the energy consumed by the load.

The Flexibility Index (FI) measures a system's ability to adapt to varying energy demands in response to price signals, thereby ensuring high energy efficiency. It reflects the impact of smart home services, intelligent building controls, and user engagement in optimizing energy use. FI is defined as the fraction of cost savings achieved by a penalty-aware operational strategy ($C_{flexible}$) compared to a penalty-restrained baseline ($C_{baseline}$) [47].

$$FI(\%) = 100 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{flexible}}{C_{baseline}}\right) \quad (16)$$

2.5.2. Economic and environmental metrics

The Net Present Value (NPV) is used to evaluate the economic feasibility of a building/community with a PV system and battery storage because it accounts for the time value of money, providing a comprehensive assessment of long-term profitability. By discounting

future cash flows, the NPV accurately reflects the financial benefits of energy savings, self-consumption, and grid interactions, while taking into account the initial investment, operational costs, and system lifetime. The NPV is calculated based on the following formula [39]:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad (17)$$

where C_t is the net cash flow in year t representing all the savings or revenues (subsidies) from PV and battery minus operational and replacement costs. r is the discount rate reflecting the time value of money. n is the considered project lifetime, and t is the year index (from 0 to n).

The Life Cycle Cost (LCC) is used to assess the total cost of ownership of a building's PV system and battery storage over its lifetime. It accounts for all relevant expenses, including initial investment, operation, maintenance, and replacement costs. By evaluating the long-term financial commitment, LCC helps compare different energy system configurations and optimize cost efficiency, ensuring sustainable and cost-effective energy planning.

$$LCC = C_{capex} + \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_{opex,t}}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_{rep,t}}{(1+r)^t} \quad (18)$$

where C_{capex} is the overall initial cost (including PV, battery, and installation...), $C_{opex,t}$ is the annual operation and maintenance costs in year t , and C_{rep} is the replacement costs for components (e.g., battery) in year t .

The environmental metrics are based on the GHG emissions, representing the carbon dioxide (CO_2) and other pollutants released into the atmosphere due to energy production and consumption. The $GHG_{avoided}$ quantifies emission reductions based on Eq. (19).

$$GHG_{avoided} = (Baseline_{grid_energy} - Actual_{grid_energy}) \cdot EF \quad (19)$$

where the $Baseline_{grid_energy}$ represents the scenario where all energy is drawn from the grid, and the $Actual_{grid_energy}$ is the actual energy consumption from the grid, accounting for the contribution of PV generation and battery storage. EF is the emissions factor for grid electricity [kg CO_2/kWh].

3. Software architecture and implementation

Building upon the theoretical framework described in Section 2, this section presents the software architecture and practical implementation of the DORES toolbox. The objective is to demonstrate how the

underlying models and control strategies have been integrated into a user-friendly, practical application that enables streamlined scenario analysis and system optimization.

3.1. High-level architecture

DORES is developed in MATLAB and structured around a modular architecture that enhances flexibility and scalability. The software is deployed as a standalone executable application (DORES_app.exe), which runs with the MATLAB Runtime environment [48], removing the need for a full MATLAB license. Fig. 3 illustrates the overall workflow and data flow within the DORES internal blocks, from data input to results visualization and export.

The first step in the workflow involves preparing the input data for simulation. DORES accepts either measured data from smart meters or simulated load profiles, as described in Section 2.1. Input files must follow a specific format, typically containing hourly data for an entire year (8,760 rows). Table 3 shows an example of the required data structure, which includes variables such as load demand, PV system output, ambient temperature, solar irradiance, and electricity prices. At a minimum, the input file must contain a time vector, global horizontal irradiance (G_h), and ambient temperature (T_a) in order to run the simulations.

The second step involves the data handling unit, where the input file is verified. Based on its contents, the software enables or restricts certain features. In this step, the user can also review the loaded data, select the analysis period, and choose an appropriate consumption profile for the case study.

The third step focuses on designing and sizing the PV and EES systems. Here, the user also defines parameters related to location, grid constraints, and economic conditions.

The fourth block is dedicated to the simulation and operation of a single building based on the inputs defined in the previous steps. This block allows users to test different control strategies and compare multiple scenarios. It also enables rapid scaling of energy sources such as PV systems and EES, helping to assess their impact on KPIs. Moreover, this block can generate multiple output files (building passports) stored in a dedicated folder (see Step 5 in the flowchart). These files can then be

Table 3

Example of input data structure required by DORES.

Variable	Definition	Unit
Time	Annual date time vector in hourly resolution.	dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm
Load	Measured data of the building's electrical load.	Watts
PV1	Measured data of the 1st PV system installed on the roof	Watts
PV2	Measured data of the 2nd PV system installed on the roof	Watts
PVFE	Measured data of the PV system installed on the East façade	Watts
PVFW	Measured data of the PV system installed on the West façade	Watts
PVFS	Measured data of the PV system installed on the South façade	Watts
Elec. Price	Day-ahead electricity prices, including distribution fees	Euro/MWh
Gh	Global horizontal irradiance at the building location	W/m ²
Ta	Ambient temperature at the building location	°C
WS	Wind speed data in the building location	m/s

used directly in the EC simulation Tab (Block 7).

Building passport files can either be generated by repeating Steps 1 to 4 or imported from measured data or previous analyses (as shown in Step 6).

Block 7, dedicated to the Energy Community Simulation Tab, offers functionalities similar to those in the single-building simulation Tab. Users can simulate aggregated buildings collectively and apply rapid scaling of energy sources to observe changes in community-level KPIs. This block also supports the generation of multiple output files representing various EC configurations and performance indicators.

Thanks to its modular architecture and simplified input structure, DORES offers high flexibility in simulating both individual buildings and entire ECs, with no limitation on the number of buildings. Furthermore, if sufficient data is available, the EC analysis can be performed directly without first running a single-building simulation.

Fig. 3. High-level architecture and operation of the DORES tool.

Fig. 4. The different tabs of the software user interface.

3.2. User interface overview

The Graphical User Interface (GUI) is organized into six main tabs (see Fig. 4), each corresponding to a key workflow stage: i) Data Preparation, ii) Energy Sources & Settings, iii) Building Simulation, iv) Building Visualization, v) Energy Community Simulation, and vi) Energy Community Visualization. Each tab includes tooltips, default values, and drop-downs to guide the user. In addition, the number of buttons used was limited to the minimum to enhance the software’s ergonomics. All modeling and simulation methods used in the GUI correspond to the detailed formulations presented in Section 2.

3.3. Data preparation tab

To facilitate data import, the tool supports multiple file formats, including “.mat”, “.xls”, “.xlsx”, and “.csv”. Users can upload their datasets directly into the software via the Load button, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

When measured data is not available, DORES offers pre-defined normalized load profiles that can be adapted to specific building typologies and consumption patterns. Fig. 6 displays the interface where users can select either measured or simulated profiles and define the analysis period.

Furthermore, to customize load profiles to match actual consumption values, users can apply the load profile estimation feature (Section 2.1). This is visualized in Fig. 7, where available profiles can be selected from a drop-down list.

3.4. Energy sources & settings

Following data preparation, users configure the energy system components, including PV systems, battery storage, and grid interaction parameters.

3.4.1. PV system configuration

DORES enables users to simulate various PV configurations, from simple residential arrays to complex multi-facade commercial systems. Users can define two rooftop systems and three façade-mounted systems (south, east, west), specifying key parameters such as capacity, tilt, and azimuth angles. Fig. 8 illustrates the PV configuration interface, which includes default values and manual input fields for precision.

3.4.2. Battery storage configuration

Electrical energy storage systems, such as batteries, can be configured using both technical and economic parameters, including capacity, charge/discharge rates, and cost assumptions. Fig. 9 shows the battery configuration interface, which supports both manual input and automatic sizing options. This flexibility allows users to tailor storage solutions for individual buildings or shared community systems, leveraging the dynamic battery models described in Section 2.3.

3.4.3. Grid interaction configuration

To complete the system setup, users define grid interaction parameters, such as maximum import and export capacities. Fig. 10 displays the interface where these constraints are set, enabling users to explore scenarios such as peak shaving or export limitation in alignment with regulatory requirements.

3.5. Building simulation tab

With system parameters defined, users can run building-level simulations using a range of control strategies introduced in Section 2.4, including load-following, peak shaving, and price-driven optimization algorithms. Simulations produce detailed outputs, which include energy flows, battery operation, and economic metrics.

Performance evaluation is supported through an integrated dashboard of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), illustrated in Fig. 11.

Fig. 5. Illustration of the data import process within the software and supported input file extensions.

Fig. 6. Interface for selecting measured or simulated data alongside load profile options tailored to specific building types and analysis periods.

Fig. 7. A drop-down list of available load profiles within the software.

Metrics such as self-consumption, self-sufficiency, flexibility index, cost savings, NPV, and emissions reductions are automatically calculated, providing users with comprehensive insights into system performance.

3.6. Energy community simulation tab

Beyond individual buildings, DORES enables community-scale

simulations by aggregating the results from building-level simulations. Users can import pre-simulated building files into the EC Simulation tab, specify shared energy storage configurations, and select appropriate control strategies.

As shown in Fig. 12, the interface allows for configuring prosumer and consumer profiles within the community. Users can define total installed PV capacity and storage systems to explore collective optimization strategies. Scenario comparison features enable side-by-side evaluation of different control strategies or system configurations, supporting strategic planning for EC.

3.7. Visualization

To support the interpretation of simulation outputs, DORES provides advanced visualization capabilities. As illustrated in Fig. 13, the software displays high-level summaries of energy balances, power flows, and cumulative costs. Detailed hourly results can also be accessed for more granular analysis, as shown in Fig. 14. The results, including graphs and exported files, are presented in a consistent manner for both buildings and communities to familiarize users with the output simulations and minimize the excess of information that could mislead interpretations.

The visualization tabs for buildings and communities showing their configurations support interactive adjustments, enabling users to dynamically modify PV or EES capacities and observe the immediate impact on system KPIs. Fig. 15 demonstrates this feature, which enhances the user experience by providing real-time feedback for design and strategy decisions.

Roof Photovoltaic system - 1		Roof Photovoltaic system - 2		Facade Photovoltaic system - West		Facade Photovoltaic system - South		Facade Photovoltaic system - East	
Number of modules	180	Number of modules	180	Number of modules	100	Number of modules	100	Number of modules	100
Tilt angle (deg)	35	Tilt angle (deg)	35	Tilt angle (deg)	90	Tilt angle (deg)	90	Tilt angle (deg)	90
Azimuth angle (deg)	0	Azimuth angle (deg)	0	Azimuth angle (deg)	90	Azimuth angle (deg)	0	Azimuth angle (deg)	-90
PV max. power Pm (W)	400	PV max. power Pm (W)	250	PV max. power Pm (W)	250	PV max. power Pm (W)	250	PV max. power Pm (W)	250
PV module area (m2)	1.6	PV module area (m2)	1.6	PV module area (m2)	1.6	PV module area (m2)	1.6	PV module area (m2)	1.6
NOCT	45	NOCT	45	NOCT	45	NOCT	45	NOCT	45
Temp.Coeff. Pm (%/°C)	0.45	Temp.Coeff. Pm (%/°C)	0.45	Temp.Coeff. Pm (%/°C)	0.45	Temp.Coeff. Pm (%/°C)	0.45	Temp.Coeff. Pm (%/°C)	0.45
Overall system efficiency (%)	90	Overall system efficiency (%)	90	Overall system efficiency (%)	90	Overall system efficiency (%)	90	Overall system efficiency (%)	90
PV system size (kWp)	72	PV system size (kWp)	45	PV system size (kWp)	25	PV system size (kWp)	25	PV system size (kWp)	25
PV energy generation (MWh)	0	PV energy generation (MWh)	0	PV energy generation (MWh)	8.753	PV energy generation (MWh)	19.29	PV energy generation (MWh)	0

Fig. 8. Configuration interface for defining PV system parameters.

Electrical Energy Storage (EES) System

Battery capacity (kWh)	100
SOC maximum limit (%)	95
SOC initial (%)	50
SOC minimum limit (%)	20
Maximum charging power (kW)	100
Maximum discharging power (kW)	100
Charge/discharge efficiency (%)	90
Battery amortisation cost (€/kWh)	40
Number of cycles	4000

EES size estimation

Sizing EES for: Building Community

EES operation mode: Peak-Shaving Standalone

Calculate Use

Required EES capacity (kWh)

Required EES power (kW)

Fig. 9. Configuration interface for inputting parameters related to the EES system.

Utility Grid Parameters

Grid limit maximum power (kW)	<input type="text" value="140"/>
Maximum peak power sent to the grid (kW)	<input type="text" value="1e+06"/>

Fig. 10. Configuration interface for utility grid parameters.

KPIs	
Self-sufficiency (%)	56.22
Self-consumption (%)	66.91
Peak power delivered from grid (kW)	67.08
Peak power exported to grid (kW)	116.6
Battery number of cycles	209
Battery state-of-health (SOH) (%)	95
Electricity bill (€)	1.86e+04
Simple payback period (years)	7.987
Return of investment ROI (%)	12.52
Total GHG emissions avoided (tCO2)	879.6
Annual ERI (kg CO2/Euro invested)	0.1817
Total NPV for the selected period (€)	7.526e+04
Total Life Cycle Cost (LCC) (€)	3.638e+05
Equivalent Annual Cost (EAC) (€)	2.919e+04
Total Life Cycle Cost with Disposal (€)	3.93e+05
Equivalent Annual Cost with Disposal (€)	3.154e+04
Flexibility index (%)	0

Fig. 11. Overview of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) calculated by the toolbox.

4. Validation and discussions

To ensure clarity, it is important to highlight how the validation procedure relates to the methodology described in Section 2. The PV generation model (Section 2.2) and the battery dynamics model (Section 2.3) are validated against both monitored data and a commercial tool (PV*SOL). The energy management strategies (Section 2.4) are indirectly validated through their ability to reproduce realistic operational behavior under these test cases. In contrast, some of the graphical outputs presented in Section 3 (e.g., Figs. 11–15) are included primarily as illustrative examples of the capabilities of DORES rather than as formal validation results. These figures demonstrate the types of outputs and key performance indicators available to end users, but they are not intended as analytical benchmarks. By distinguishing between validation cases and illustrative outputs, we aim to combine methodological rigor with practical insight into the tool’s functionality.

4.1. Validation against measured data

Monitored data from real buildings equipped with PV and battery storage systems were used to validate the outputs generated by DORES.

The first case study involves an administrative building constructed following near-zero energy building (NZEB) standards, featuring low energy demand [40]. It is equipped with a rooftop PV system with an installed capacity of 7.28 kWp and a lithium-ion battery energy storage system with a storage capacity of 25.2 kWh. The validation was conducted using monitored data from a period in which the building operated in stand-alone mode, i.e., with zero energy drawn from the grid. This specific timeframe, between July 2nd and 10th, was characterized by high solar generation relative to the building’s energy demand, typical for summer. During this period, the building was operated under the LFCS, whereby excess PV energy was directed to charge the battery during the day and battery discharge covered night loads. This matches the control mode implemented in the DORES software for comparability [41].

Fig. 12. Comprehensive visualization of the EC Simulation tab.

Fig. 13. Visualization of simulation results in the toolbox software (cumulative results).

Fig. 14. Example of DORES visualization outputs. The plots illustrate how detailed results are displayed within the toolbox interface, rather than representing a specific case study.

Fig. 15. Comprehensive visual interaction with the building's energy systems.

Fig. 16. Validation of PV and battery model based on real measurement data.

Fig. 17. Validation of PV and battery model based on real measurement data.

Fig. 16 compares the simulated results from DORES and the actual measured data retrieved from the monitoring energy systems portal of the building. The simulation closely mirrors the measured values for PV generation, demonstrating that DORES can accurately model rooftop PV systems. The calculated RMSE is below 2 % in this case, confirming a high level of accuracy.

When examining the system’s interaction with the grid, the results also show a good alignment in terms of excess energy exported. However, certain peaks in the measured data – where exported energy is higher or slightly shifted – may be attributed to data collection inconsistencies or inaccuracies in the measured SOC of the battery. The difference between simulated and measured grid export is around 12 %.

The lower part of Fig. 16 illustrates the evolution of the battery’s SOC. While some deviation is observed, the general trend is consistent between simulation and measurement. Importantly, the simulated SOC accurately reflects both the minimum and maximum levels recorded in the real system.

Lastly, to further assess the accuracy of DORES in simulating PV outputs from façade systems and the electrical generation of photovoltaic thermal (PVT) collectors, real monitored data from a building equipped with both rooftop PV/PVT and façade-mounted systems was used. These installations featured various tilt and azimuth angles. In this setup, all electrical outputs from the different subsystems are combined and connected to a single inverter with a total capacity of 40 kW.

Fig. 18. Designed system in PV*SOL for the comparison of the two software.

Table 4
Comparison of results from PVSOL and DORES.

Variable	PVSOL	DORES	Deviation (%)
Load consumption (kWh)	10,032	10,032	–
PV generation (kWh)	8,587	8,682	1.1
Grid energy (kWh)	3,697	3,829	–3.6
Excess energy to grid (kWh)	1,755	1,801	–2.6
Battery energy (kWh)	592	626	–5.7
Self-sufficiency (%)	63.2	61.7	2.4
Self-consumption (%)	79.7	77	3.4
Total system losses (%)	11.8	12.1	–2.1

Fig. 17 illustrates the validation results, comparing DORES simulations with the actual measured data. The deviation between the simulated and monitored PV energy was found to be less than 6 %, with a calculated RMSE of 4.14 %. These results confirm the reliability of DORES in accurately reproducing the performance of complex PV configurations, including façade and hybrid PV/PVT systems.

While this standalone validation demonstrates the accuracy of the PV and battery models under constrained operation, it represents only one specific use case. It provides a solid basis for future validation of other control strategies (e.g., peak shaving and SEMS) at both the building scale and, as data become available, at the community scale.

4.2. Benchmarking against commercial tools

To further evaluate the reliability of DORES, its simulation outputs were compared with those from PV*SOL premium, a widely used commercial software for PV system design and simulation [22]. For this comparison, a generic residential building model was used, featuring both roof-integrated and façade-integrated PV systems. The rooftop installation includes 10 standard monocrystalline panels, each with a capacity of 400 W, while the façade-based BIPV system consists of 6 similar panels. The building was also equipped with a 24 kWh battery storage system. To ensure consistency, the same household consumption profile, selected from PV*SOL's predefined load profiles, was applied in both simulation environments. The 3D model of the house with its PV installations is shown in Fig. 18.

As shown in Table 4, DORES produced results closely aligned with PV*SOL across all key technical performance indicators. The deviation

in PV generation was only 1.1 %, while the differences in grid interaction metrics (grid energy and excess to the grid) remained within 3–4 %. Battery-related performance and system indicators such as Ss and Sc showed comparable accuracy, confirming the fidelity of DORES' integrated simulation models.

While this benchmarking confirms consistency with a widely recognized tool, it should not be regarded as definitive validation. Importantly, DORES extends beyond PV*SOL by enabling community-scale simulations, flexible control strategy comparisons, and integrated techno-economic-environmental analysis, which are not fully supported in commercial tools.

5. Discussion

5.1. Results interpretation and practical implications

The validation results confirm that DORES provides a reliable and flexible environment for simulating PV and battery storage systems in buildings and communities. Benchmarking against measured data and PV*SOL demonstrated high accuracy: deviations in self-consumption, self-sufficiency, and grid dependency indicators remained within 5 %, validating DORES as a credible decision-support tool for energy planners, engineers, and researchers.

A core objective of DORES is to support the design of systems that maximize on-site renewable energy utilization while enhancing energy autonomy. The simulation scenarios demonstrated that the integration of appropriately sized battery storage and advanced control strategies can significantly increase self-consumption rates and reduce grid reliance. By allowing straightforward comparison of control strategies, DORES helps users understand operational trade-offs, helping to optimize both technical performance and economic outcomes [25].

Economically, DORES facilitates robust financial evaluations through key metrics such as Net Present Value (NPV) and Life Cycle Cost (LCC). These indicators enable users balance capital investments with operational savings and potential revenues from surplus energy exports. The tools also quantifies CO₂ savings, supporting broader sustainability goals by quantifying the environmental impact of different system configurations [29]. Furthermore, the ability to model both individual buildings and aggregated ECs enables the exploration of local energy-sharing schemes, which are increasingly relevant under emerging policy frameworks promoting prosumer collaboration.

In terms of computational performance and scalability, DORES remain efficient when extending from building to community-scale simulations. On a standard PC (Intel i7, 16 GB RAM), a one-year hourly simulation for a single building executes in less than 20 s, while a 50-building community completes in under 2 min. Runtime scales approximately linearly with the number of buildings, making large-scale scenario testing feasible. The modular architecture, based on “building passports” aggregated for ECs, support this scalability, with performance limited mainly by the availability of high-resolution load and PV data, rather than computational power. Rule-based strategies execute even faster.

By integrating these capabilities into an accessible and user-friendly platform, DORES supports a wide range of stakeholders in making informed decisions that advance the adoption of sustainable, resilient energy systems.

5.2. Comparison with existing tools

In the evolving field of PV and battery system modeling, a range of tools has been developed, each with distinct strengths and limitations. Commercial solutions such as HOMER Pro, PV*SOL, and SAM are widely used due to their validated performance and strong techno-economic features. HOMER Pro excels in microgrid sizing and dispatch, but offers limited support for community-level modeling and advanced emissions accounting [49]. PV*SOL provides high-fidelity PV yield

simulations with shading analysis [22], though its representation of battery behavior is relatively simplified. SAM includes detailed financial modeling and sub-hourly simulations [23]; however, automated sizing and user-defined control strategies are limited, and its focus lies primarily on single-system rather than community-scale applications.

Academic and open-source tools, such as SAMA, DER-CAM, Ficus, and ESN, offer greater modeling flexibility. For example, SAMA supports multi-objective optimization and has been validated against HOMER [25], while DER-CAM applies mixed-integer linear programming for the co-optimization of distributed energy resources [50]. Yet, these research-grade tools often require advanced expertise and programming skills, which can restrict accessibility for broader user groups.

Unlike these tools, DORES combines the flexibility of research frameworks with the usability of commercial software. It supports scenario testing of advanced control strategies, automated load profile generation, battery sizing, a comprehensive KPIs framework (technical, economic, and environmental), and multi-scale capability. This positions DORES as a complementary solution that integrates the accuracy of validated tools with broader functionality and accessibility.

Concrete user benefits illustrate this added value. For example, DORES enables users to directly quantify how battery storage increases self-sufficiency, reduces grid reliance, lowers CO₂ emissions, and improves financial indicators compared to PV-only configurations. Switching between control strategies such as LFCS and PSCS produces immediate comparative KPIs for self-sufficiency and peak demand, allowing users to explore operational trade-offs efficiently.

Beyond quantitative benchmarking, DORES distinguishes itself by combining detailed PV and battery modeling, advanced control strategy testing, and community-scale simulations within a single platform. This combination of flexibility and accessibility positions it as a complementary tool that fills the gap between specialized academic models and rigid commercial software.

5.3. Limitations and future directions

Despite these strengths, several limitations remain in the current version of DORES, which guide future development priorities. At this stage, simulations are performed at an hourly resolution, which is generally sufficient for preliminary design and assessment. However, for more advanced applications (such as implementing smart energy management strategies or providing ancillary services to the grid), a finer temporal resolution, such as 15-minute timesteps, would offer more precise results.

The battery aging model relies on cumulative full equivalent cycles calculation and does not yet capture electrochemical degradation mechanisms such as capacity fading due to depth-of-discharge variations or temperature impacts. While suitable for high-level economic evaluations, this approach may overlook important aspects of long-term battery performance. Likewise, DORES assumes uniform irradiance across PV modules and does not currently model the impacts of partial shading or soiling. Although this assumption improves computational efficiency, it can lead to slight overestimations of PV output in dense urban settings.

Currently, DORES is tailored to PV systems (rooftop and façade) and electrical battery storage, reflecting the most common configurations in buildings and communities. This is a limitation, as other renewable sources (e.g., small-scale wind, PV-thermal collectors) and storage options (thermal storage, electric vehicles with smart charging/V2G) are increasingly relevant. Extending the tool to incorporate these technologies is part of the planned development roadmap, which would broaden its applicability and enable multi-energy and sector-coupling analyses.

Another important limitation concerns validation at the energy community scale. While DORES has been designed to support aggregated load and generation modeling as well as shared storage strategies, the present study focused on validating single-building cases due to the

availability of monitored datasets. Community-scale validation was not feasible because of the lack of operational energy community data and the absence of commercial tools offering comparable benchmarking features. Future work will address this gap by applying DORES to ongoing pilot projects, enabling direct testing and validation of aggregation effects, shared storage performance, and advanced community-level control strategies.

At the EC level, DORES aggregates loads and generation across buildings and performs economic analysis for the EC as a whole. However, it does not yet support the distribution of benefits or costs among individual prosumers/prosumers, as this would require the integration of detailed business models and alignment with national policies and regulatory frameworks governing community energy.

Planned developments will also include the integration of electric vehicles with smart charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) interactions, advanced EC modeling with smart aggregation of buildings, peer-to-peer energy trading functionalities, dynamic pricing scenarios, and policy simulations. These enhancements aim to expand the scope and realism of DORES, making it a more powerful and flexible tool for the design and operation of sustainable energy systems.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented a comprehensive overview of DORES – Design and Operation of Renewable Energy Systems – a novel simulation and decision-support toolbox for optimizing PV and energy storage systems in the built environment. By bridging the gap between commercial solutions and academic research models, DORES provides an accessible yet powerful platform for analyzing the technical, economic, and environmental aspects of renewable energy integration.

Thanks to its flexible architecture and user-friendly user interface, DORES allows users to simulate a wide range of scenarios, including diverse building typologies, varying energy demands, and different control strategies. Its ability to automatically generate load profiles, size storage systems, and evaluate advanced energy management approaches enables users to design systems that optimize self-consumption, enhance energy autonomy, and improve cost-effectiveness. Importantly, the integration of key performance indicators (KPIs) such as Net Present Value (NPV), Life Cycle Cost (LCC), and CO₂ emissions reductions allows for a comprehensive assessment of both economic and environmental impacts.

Validation against both measured data and established simulation platforms, such as PV*SOL, confirmed the accuracy and reliability of DORES. Comparative analysis with existing tools further highlights its position as a versatile solution, suitable for applications ranging from feasibility studies and academic research to policy evaluation and real-world energy system design.

Beyond serving as a practical software tool, DORES also introduces methodological innovations, such as multi-scale modeling, SEMS strategies, integration of battery wear costs, and a holistic KPI framework, which advance current approaches and distinguish it from existing platforms.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sofiane Kichou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization.
Nikolaos Skandalos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, Call Excellent Research, and the project “Climate Positive Circular Communities, ARV” funded by the H2020 EU-funded under the agreement ID: 101036723.

Data availability

DORES software related to this article can be found at <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/j8s85r7fm/1> an open-source online data repository hosted at Mendeley Data.

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